

PERSONALITY AND LOWER CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

Vikaras (Evil) are, the five major weaknesses of the human personality at variance. These are Kaam (Lust), Krodh (Rage), Lobh (Greed), Maoh (Attachment), Ahankar (Ego). Ego is a one of the dominating evil of human life. Egotism is the negative tendency of a person to speak and to think of oneself excessively and boastfully. The egotist has an overwhelming sense of the centrality of the "ME": of person's personal qualities. The personality consists of the three elements i.e. id, ego and superego. The key to a healthy personality is the balance between ego and the reality of the real world. People differ in terms of the extent to which their personality is dominated by ego. Personality is the deeply ingrained and relatively enduring patterns of thoughts, feelings and behavior. Personality usually refers to something that is unique about a person, the characteristics that distinguish him or her from other people. Personality implies predictability about how a person will act or react under different circumstances. Therefore, the purpose of the investigation is to distinct the types of personality and their level of egotism.

The sample of the present study consisted of 200 cases. Both male (50 extrovert and 50 introvert) and female (50 extrovert and 50 introvert) respondents of 40 to 60 years have been conveniently selected. In the present study Egotism Scale developed by Das & Sisodia (2011) and Introversion Extroversion Inventory (Hindi) developed by Aziz & Gupta (1923) is used. Mann-Whitney U test was used. Results reveal that Extrovert Personality people have more egotism ($M= 13.68$) than Introvert Personality people ($M= 11.47$), and the obtained Mann-Whitney U value ($Z_u= 2.369, p < 0.01$) is significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Introduction:

In some ways all human beings are all the same. Everyone has the same human nature. Every one shares a common humanity. All human beings have human bodies, human minds, as well as human thoughts and human feelings. Yet in other ways every human being is different and unique. No two people are exactly alike. No two people can ever have the same experience of life, the same perspective, the same mind. Thus personality is about our different ways of being human. The human nature generally manifests in different styles of thinking, feeling and acting.

Personality can be defined as a dynamic and organized set of characteristics possessed by a person that uniquely influences his or her cognitions, motivations, and behaviors in various situations. Personality is the deeply ingrained and relatively enduring patterns of thought, feeling and behavior. Personality usually refers to something that is unique about a person, the characteristics that distinguish him or her from other people. It can also be defined as consistency in a person's way of being — that is, long-term consistency in their particular ways of perceiving, thinking, acting and reacting as a person. To some extent, people generally do tend to operate in a similar way day after day, year after year which shows overall patterns, tendencies, inclinations of a person towards life. Someone who has tended to be quiet and reserved up to now will probably be quiet and reserved in future also. A brief definition would be that personality is made up of the characteristic patterns of thoughts, feelings and behaviors that make a person unique. In addition to this, personality arises from within the individual and remains fairly consistent throughout life.

There are two types of personality: (1) Extrovert Personality, (2) Introvert Personality. Extroversion is the act, state, or habit of being predominantly concerned with the obtaining gratification from what is outside the self. An extrovert is someone who likes to be social and whose interests mostly lie with things beyond him/herself, such as other people and the physical environment. Extroverts are not as concerned with themselves and thus do not focus much on their own thoughts or feelings. Extrovert people are often emotional, impulsive (doing something suddenly based on an urge), confident about themselves in social situations, and are

involved in the lives of others. This behaviors include acting, talking, assertiveness, adventurous and outgoing . According to Jung (1921), “Extroversion as turning the interests and energies of the mind toward events, people, and things in the world.”

Introversion is one of the major personality traits, identifies in many theories of personality. People who are introvert tend to be inward turning, or focused more on internal thoughts, feelings and moods rather than seeking out external stimulation. Introvert people are more concerned with the inner world of the mind. They enjoy thinking, exploring their thoughts and feelings. They have an inward focus and usually do not like the social gathering. They have a strong sense of self that can make them feel highly self- conscious around other people. Generally, introverts process their emotions, thoughts and observations internally. Introverts are more private, and less public. Introverts need time to think before responding to a situation, and develop their ideas by reflecting privately. Introverts’ personality traits can be passionate, but not usually aggressive.

Introverts usually tend to get their energy from within. After a day filled with people or activities, introverts tend to feel exhausted and empty. To recharge their energy introverts need to be alone reading, daydreaming, painting or gardening and any solo activity fills them up again. This doesn’t mean introvert have to live alone in a cave in the hills or on Walden Pond; they just need quite time to come back to themselves. The energy source for introverts is from within.

Extrovert Vs Introvert:

Extroverts are directed towards the objective world whereas Introverts are directed towards the subjective world. The most common differences between Extroverts and Introverts are shown below:

- Extroverts are interested in what is happening around them and Introverts are interested in their own thoughts and feelings.
- Extroverts are open and often talkative and compare their own opinions with the opinions of others whereas Introverts are needed to have own territory and often appear reserved, quiet and thoughtful.

- Extroverts have tendency to make new friends easily, adapt to a new group and like to say whatever they think whereas Introverts have difficulties in making new contacts and feel shy and keep themselves quite.

EGO:

Egotism is an inflated sense of “importance” or “greatness”, i.e.: someone whose thoughts always go around declaring himself how great he is. Egotism is simply motivated by self-interest. An egotist is someone who feels as if he or she is superior to others in all aspects of personality. Egotism implies that a person care about him or herself and for his or her own welfare and has exaggerated opinion about his or her own importance. Egotism, is actually a mask person wears to hide the faults and weaknesses. Carlyle (1795- 1881) wrote, “Egotism is the source and summary of all faults and miseries.” Therefore one must take care not to become trapped in the imaginary world of superiority and inferiority.

Egotism is an inflated, perhaps untenable or unstable, view of self. Egotism is typically operationalized as narcissism (Bhusman and Baumeister, 1998, 2002) or as one of its more destructive variants, including narcissistic entitlement (Campbell et al., 2004), narcissism in conjunction with low self- concept clarity (Stucke and Sporer, 2002), or narcissism with self esteem partialled out (Paulhus, Robins, Trzesniewski, and Tracy, 2004).

The eventual understanding that immediate gratification is usually impossible (and often unwise) comes with the formation of the ego, which is ruled by the *reality principle*. The ego acts as a between in the id's relations with reality, often suppressing the id's urges until an appropriate situation arises. This repression of inappropriate desires and urges represents the greatest strain on, and the most important function of, the mind. The ego often utilizes defense mechanisms to achieve and aid this repression. Where the id may have an urge and form a picture which satisfies this urge, the ego engages in a strategy to actually fulfill the urge. The thirsty five-year-old now not only identifies water as the satisfaction of his urge, but forms a plan to obtain water, perhaps by finding a drinking fountain. While the ego is still in the service of the id, it borrows some of its psychic energy in an effort to control the urge until it is feasibly satisfied. The ego's efforts at pragmatic satisfaction of urges eventually builds a great number of

skills and memories and becomes aware of itself as an entity. With the formation of the ego, the individual becomes a self, instead of an amalgamation of urges and needs. The ego deals with reality, trying to meet the desires of the id in a way that is socially acceptable in the world. This may mean delaying gratification, and helping to get rid of the tension the id feels if a desire is not met right away. The ego recognizes that other people have needs and wants too, and that being selfish is not always good for us in the long run.

Objectives:

- To study the difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality.

Hypotheses:

- There is no significant difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality.

Variables:

Independent Variables

- Introvert Personality
- Extrovert Personality

Dependent Variable

- Egotism

Control Variables

- Age (40- 60 years)
- Gender (Male and Female both)
- Academic Qualification (At least Graduate)

Sample Description: The sample of the present study will consist of 200 subjects. Both male (50 extrovert and 50 introvert) and female (50 extrovert and 50 introvert) respondents are conveniently selected of the 40 to 60 age groups. .

Tools:

- 1) **Egotism Scale:** - Egotism Scale is constructed by Das and Sisodia (2011). It provides a useful way to measure that how much an individual is egoistic. The validity of this test is high. The total number of questions in this scale is 30. The criterion related validity is 0.65 and construct validity is 0.24. Reliability coefficient of correlation is $r = .1$ and the test retest reliability is .55.
- 2) **Introversion- Extroversion Inventory (In Hindi):-** This scale is developed by Aziz and Agnihotry (1923) to measure that individual is extrovert or introvert. Reliability of this test is .91 and the validity coefficient obtained is .95, which is significant beyond .01 level. The total number of questions in this scale is 60.

Result:

The present research is aimed to compare the Egotism of Introvert and Extrovert type of personality people. The raw data has been analyzed on the basis of Mann- Whitney U test.

Table-1
Mean and Zu for Egotism of Two Personality:

Personalities	N	Mean	Zu	Level Of Significance
Extrovert Personality	100	13.68	2.369	p < 0.05
Introvert Personality	100	11.47		

N= 100 people with 50 males and 50 females in each group.

Table depicts the mean scores, Z_u of Extrovert Personalities and Introvert Personality on Egotism. Table 1 shows that Extrovert Personality have considerably high Egotism ($M= 13.68$) as compared Introvert Personality ($M= 11.47$). The obtained Mann-Whitney U value ($Z_u= 2.369$, $p < 0.05$) is highly significant at 0.05 level of significance, which suggests that there is a significant difference between the two groups of personality on Egotism. Hence, the hypothesis which stated that, “There is no significant difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality”, is rejected.

Figure- 1

Mean Scores of Egotism of Two Groups of Personalities

Conclusion:

The finding of the present result reveals that there is significant difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality. It leads to the rejection of hypothesis that there is no significant difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality. The mean value of the present finding shows that egotism is higher in Extrovert Personality than

Introvert. **Adams & Nelson et al. (1984)** also studied personality types using the Myers- Briggs type indicator. They found that extroverted showed more social interaction than the introverted group. As it is very fact that in ego the mind lives in the delusionary world of the self importance and self absorption. Egotism is an inflated sense of importance and motivated by self interest. It is an observed fact that the persons of extrovert personality are impulsive, social, open, often talkative and compare their own opinion with the opinions of others that shows his greatness and importance which are the key characteristics of the egotism itself.

Findings:

After the analyses of the present investigation, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Egotism is more in Extrovert type than introvert type personality people.
- There is significant difference of egotism between extrovert and introvert types of personality.

Limitations:

- The study was conducted on a limited sample of 200 people from Agra city only.
- The study has not been done on the people below 40 and above 60 in age group, so results cannot be generalized on other groups.
- Rural areas are not included in the sample, so the scope of the study is restricted.

Implication Of The Study:

When the controller is the senses the mind then it results in worldly attraction leading to Kaam (Lust), Krodh (Anger), Moh (Attachment), Lobh (Greed) and Ahankar (Ego). The master of the mind is the soul and the slaves of the mind are the senses. The property is to move and produce two fold movements- Inward and Outward. When outward then it is towards worldly materialistic attraction and controlled by ego. The inward flow of energy can hindered by an inflated feeling of pride of being superior to others, called Ego. On these assumptions investigator wanted to know, which type of personality governs with senses.

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